

The Effect of History Teachers on Students' Career Choices

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Abstract

This study investigates the methodological culture of history teaching through the perspectives of history teacher trainees at J. Selye University in Slovakia. The research aims to identify the teaching methods students encountered during their secondary history education and to examine who most influenced their decision to pursue a teaching career. Based on responses from 83 participants, 58% indicated that a former history teacher played a significant role in their career choice. Statistical analysis confirmed that those influenced by history teachers had experienced a more diverse set of instructional methods during their high school years. Additionally, 69% of participants expressed a preference for applying non-frontal teaching methods in their future careers, with this intention being significantly more pronounced among master's students (93%) compared to bachelor's students (55%). These findings suggest that both the influence of inspiring teachers and university training contribute to a shift toward a more collaborative and student-centred methodology in history education. The results underscore the importance of diverse, interactive teaching strategies in fostering key student competencies and potentially transforming the pedagogical culture of history teaching soon.

Keywords: *history education, teaching methodology, career choice, student-centred learning, cooperative learning, former history teacher.*

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Introduction

Today, the needs of young people differ significantly from those of fifty years ago, and pedagogy must keep pace with this rapid change. According to the dialogical theory, learning is realized through the mutually and collaboratively created or modified content, where the focus is not solely on participation or acquisition, nor exclusively on the individual or the community, but rather on the process through which participants collaboratively construct shared knowledge (Paavola, Hakkarainen 2005).

The necessity for pedagogy to catch up with societal changes, and the emphasis on this need, has been a subject of research and public education policy discussions for at least two decades. As Józsa and Székely (2004, 339. p.) argue, "Criticism is being formulated

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regarding the content and methods of traditional education. A significant portion of students fail to reach the desired level of skill development. They are unmotivated and perceive school learning as boring and burdensome. It seems that traditional pedagogical methods are insufficient for success.”

Selecting and applying methods that are aligned with the teacher’s personality, educational goals, and students’ needs is a vital part of the teaching process. Among the new generation of educational methods are project-based learning, cooperative methods, and technology-assisted approaches involving computers, the internet, and multimedia. The most defining characteristic of these new generation methods is that they are based on collaboration (Szili 2013).

However, the pursuit of collaboration presents new challenges for educators, as the traditional teacher role is also undergoing transformation. Most teachers do not perceive the pedagogical activities resulting from this changing teacher role as a positive opportunity (Ferenczi 1998; Czike 2005; Kaposi 2020a), as the new so-called facilitator role does not seem attractive to those who primarily rely on knowledge-transmission methods. This may be due to the fact that most teachers are not prepared for this role, and they are not convinced that these new methods would be more effective in preparing their students (Juhász, Kaposi, Szőke-Milinte 2020).

Literature Review

Tóth and Horváth (2021) draw attention to the transformed learning environment. Kaposi (2017) also emphasizes this change, arguing that we are currently witnessing a pedagogical cultural shift in which the focus of teaching and learning is increasingly placed on knowledge acquisition and processing skills, critical thinking, communication, and the intention to foster collaboration.

These changes are also evident in the teaching of history. In this context, Vajda (2018, 19. p.) points out that "the acquisition of new knowledge can be effectively achieved through different sources and mediums. Students themselves can become sources of knowledge, and the medium may differ from the traditional textbook. A history education that relies entirely on the teacher and the textbook is considered an outdated method."

Since the beginning of the 21st century – and continuing into the present – educational science literature has consistently highlighted the ability to collaborate as an essential student competency (Bognár 2002; *Key Competencies* 2002, 20-21. p.; Orbán Józsefné 2011; Binkley et al. 2012; Vass 2020). One way to foster this competency is through the application of cooperative learning in the classroom, which has gained increasing legitimacy in modern education. According to Johnson and Johnson (1994, 2003), the entire concept of cooperative learning is based on learning through group activities, where the success of individual students

Contemporary teaching strategies focus on the question, “Why and how do we want to teach?” This inquiry encourages researchers to explore individual classroom cultures and their diversity, considering students’ backgrounds, experiences, knowledge, environments, and learning goals (Serroukh, Serroukh, 2015, 2. p.).

Muijs and Reynolds (2005) argue that modern teaching methods are effective because students learn in a socially interactive environment and become independent learners

(in Serroukh, Serroukh, 2015, 2. p.). But why do many believe that non-frontal forms of instruction are more effective than the traditional frontal teaching method?

In recent decades, there has been a surge in research focused on student collaboration within the classroom (Lou et al. 1996; Gillies, Boyle 2010, 2011; Norman 2017; Pangantihon, Tantiado 2024; Karmina, Dyson, Setyowati 2024). These studies primarily examine how student interaction and collaboration influence learning outcomes and group problem-solving.

Despite the recognized benefits of cooperative methods, some studies suggest the opposite. Óhidy (2005) highlights the overcrowded curricula, the forced pace, and the time-consuming nature of experiential methods, which often lead to their limited use. Taqi and Al Nouh (2021) note several disadvantages of cooperative learning, such as the unequal distribution of work—some students receive praise despite contributing very little, while others complete the majority of the task. They also emphasize that noise is a significant drawback that discourages many teachers from implementing group work.

It is clear that experiential learning methods have both advantages and disadvantages, which educators must carefully consider before integrating them into the educational process. It is the responsibility of the teacher to choose methods and didactic elements during their lessons that promote the development of social and interpersonal competencies within the framework of historical literacy. According to Kaposi (2020b), these elements include openness, empathy, social cooperation, creativity, a reflective attitude, social sensitivity, a sense of responsibility, positive thinking, and ethical awareness.

Research Objectives and Research Questions

The primary aim of this research was to explore what types of teaching methods and learning activities current history teacher trainees (as of 2023) encountered during their secondary school history lessons. The objectives of the study are twofold: (1) to examine who had the greatest influence on students of history education at J. Selye University in Slovakia in their decision to pursue a career as history teachers, and (2) to map the types of instructional methods and forms of classroom work these students experienced during their secondary education in history classes.

(Q1) Who had the greatest influence on the students in their decision to choose the history teaching profession?

(Q1) What instructional methods and classroom work formats did students encounter during their secondary school history education?

Description of the Research Sample and Methodology

The research was conducted using the questionnaire method. The students completed the questionnaires in paper-based format, after which the responses were entered electronically and processed using the SPSS statistical software. The research can be considered representative, as the sample consisted of all history teacher training students enrolled at J. Selye University. A self-developed questionnaire was used for the purposes of the study.

The questionnaire consisted of a total of 20 questions. The research was carried out at J. Selye University in Slovakia in 2023. A total of 83 history teacher training students participated in the research, distributed across the academic years as follows: 18

students from the first year of the bachelor's programme; 14 students from the second year; 22 students from the third year; 10 students from the first year of the master's programme; and 19 students from the second year of the master's programme. The total number of students enrolled in the programme across all five academic years was 89, meaning that the response rate was exceptionally high. Among the respondents, 44 were male and 39 were female (Table 1).

Table 1. Gender Distribution of Prospective Teachers Participating in the Research by Academic Year

Gender	1st year	2nd year	3rd year	4th year	5th year	Total
Male	9	7	11	6	11	44
Female	9	7	11	4	8	39
Total	18	14	22	10	19	83

Source: Own table

Results

We aimed to explore who had the greatest effect on the students in choosing to pursue a degree in history education. The responses to this research question (Q1) are illustrated in Figure 1.

A total of 14 students indicated that their families had the greatest influence on their decision (in 6 cases it was one of the parents, while in 8 cases another relative). Eight students reported being influenced by a teacher who did not teach history (in 2 cases it was their former homeroom teacher, in 5 cases another subject teacher, and in 1 case a private tutor). Twelve students stated that the decision was entirely their own and that no one had influenced them. In one case, a public figure was identified as the source of inspiration.

The majority of respondents—48 students, representing 58% of the total sample—reported that their history teacher had a decisive influence on their decision to pursue a career in teaching and to specialize in history. This indicates that the impact of history teachers on students' career choices is statistically significant (One-Sided $p < 0.001$; Two-Sided $p < 0.001$).

Figure 1. Distribution of Individuals Who Had the Most Influence on Students' Career Choice. n = 83

Source: own figure

We aimed to map how frequently students encountered specific teaching methods during their secondary school history lessons. A total of 20 methods were listed, based on the study by Seres and Makádi (2022). For each method, participants were asked to indicate how often they had experienced it in their history classes during secondary school, choosing from the following options: “never,” “a few times per year,” “a few times per month,” or “almost every lesson.”

The responses to this question were analyzed and compared from two perspectives. First, we examined the responses of those students who reported that their history teacher had influenced their decision to choose the history teaching programme. Second, we analyzed the responses of those students who stated that their history teacher had *not* influenced this decision. The results of this analysis are presented in percentage distribution in Table 2. For each method, we indicate the percentage of students who encountered it, based on the response categories (frequency of occurrence). Each frequency level includes two columns: (1) HT, and (2) NHT. HT refers to those students who were influenced by their **H**istory **T**eacher in their career choice; NHT refers to those students who were **n**ot influenced by their history teacher in this regard.

Table 2. Percentage Distribution of Exposure to Various Teaching Methods Based on Whether or Not the Former History Teacher Influenced Students' Career Choice (n = 83)

	Never		A few times per year		A few times per month		Almost every lesson	
	HT	NHT	HT	NHT	HT	NHT	HT	NHT
1. Teacher Explanation	0	0	0	3%	10%	6%	90%	91%
2. Teacher Explanation with Presentation	4%	23%	21%	17%	35%	29%	40%	31%
3. Blackboard Outline	8%	23%	15%	14%	37%	31%	40%	31%
4. Note-Taking and Outline Creation	8%	11%	2%	14%	27%	6%	63%	67%
5. Text Analysis	15%	31%	31%	17%	44%	43%	10%	9%
6. Data and Dataset Analysis	21%	37%	44%	31%	35%	29%	0	3%
7. Image and Diagram Analysis	15%	23%	35%	34%	38%	40%	12%	3%
8. Map Analysis	4%	17%	42%	34%	35%	40%	20%	9%
9. Film/Video Analysis	27%	43%	54%	31%	19%	26%	0	0
10. Study and Analysis of Pre-Made Models and Mock-Ups	85%	77%	13%	23%	2%	0	0	0
11. Drawing	48%	46%	37%	43%	15%	11%	0	0
12. Student Inquiry and Experimentation	52%	54%	35%	37%	13%	6%	0	3%
13. Teacher Demonstration of Inquiry or Experiment	44%	66%	39%	23%	15%	11%	2%	0
14. Creation of Models and Mock-Ups	87%	83%	13%	17%	0	0	0	0
15. Use of Animations and Simulations	69%	74%	25%	17%	4%	6%	2%	3%
16. Drama-Based Pedagogical Methods (e.g., Debates)	44%	40%	23%	46%	31%	14%	2%	0

17. Media Education Methods (e.g., Advertisement Analysis or Creation)	67%	63%	29%	23%	2%	14%	2%	0
18. Field Trips, Museum Visits, and Fieldwork	15%	34%	77%	60%	6%	6%	2%	0
19. Student Presentations	27%	23%	29%	51%	38%	26%	6%	0
20. Project-Based Learning / Project Method	42%	63%	35%	20%	15%	14%	8%	3%

Source: Own table

It is evident that, in most cases, the frequency of the application of various methods is perceived to be higher among those students who reported that their former history teacher influenced their decision to pursue a degree in history. This suggests that, within the examined sample, the use of a more diverse methodological repertoire may have an impact on students' career choices.

In the next step, the responses were divided into two categories: (1) students had encountered the given method during their secondary school history lessons ("a few times a year," "a few times a month," "almost every lesson"), or (2) they had not encountered it ("never"). The results of these responses are presented in Table 3, arranged in descending order. For each method, the percentage of students who had experienced the method at least once during their secondary education is displayed. Following each method, two columns are presented: (1) HT, and (2) NHT.

HT: students whose career choice was influenced by their history teacher;

NHT: students whose career choice was not influenced by their history teacher.

Table 3. Percentage Distribution of Students' Exposure to Teaching Methods during Secondary School, Based on Who Influenced Their Career Choice (n=83)

	Were these methods used?	
	HT	NHT
1. Teacher Explanation	100%	100%
2. Teacher Explanation with Presentation	96%	77%
8. Map Analysis	96%	83%
3. Blackboard Outline	92%	77%
4. Note-Taking and Outline Creation	92%	89%
5. Text Analysis	85%	69%
7. Image and Diagram Analysis	85%	77%
18. Field Trips, Museum Visits, and Fieldwork	85%	66%
6. Data and Dataset Analysis	79%	63%
9. Film/Video Analysis	73%	57%
19. Student Presentations	73%	77%
20. Project-Based Learning / Project Method	58%	37%
13. Teacher Demonstration of Inquiry or Experiment	56%	34%
16. Drama-Based Pedagogical Methods (e.g., Debates)	56%	60%
11. Drawing	52%	54%
12. Student Inquiry and Experimentation	48%	46%
17. Media Education Methods (e.g., Advertisement Analysis or Creation)	33%	37%

15. Use of Animations and Simulations	31%	26%
10. Study and Analysis of Pre-Made Models and Mock-Ups	15%	23%
14. Creation of Models and Mock-Ups	13%	17%

Source: own table

In Table 3, we can see that all students encountered the method of teacher explanation during their secondary school history classes. However, for 13 out of the other 19 methods, the percentage distribution is higher among those students whose history teacher had an influence on their choice to pursue the history teaching program at university. From this, we can conclude that students who were influenced by their history teacher in choosing the history teaching profession encountered a more diverse range of methods during their secondary school history classes compared to those who were not influenced by their history teacher.

It is also worth examining whether there is a correlation between the highest level of education attained by the parents and the influence the parents had on the students' decision to choose the history teaching program. To do this, we first need to look at the highest level of education attained by the parents (Table 4). Out of the 83 students, 19 students' mothers and 11 students' fathers have at least a college (Bc.) degree. There are four students whose both parents hold at least a college (Bc.) degree, meaning a total of 26 students (31%) have at least one parent with a college (Bc.) degree. In Table 4, we have marked in green those students whose at least one parent has at least a basic university degree.

Among the 26 students whose at least one parent holds a tertiary education degree, 11 students reported that their former history teacher had an influence on their decision to choose the history teaching program at university, while 15 students indicated that their decision was not influenced by their history teacher (Figure 1; Table 4 - Appendix). The parents' educational level (which we categorized into two groups due to the sample size: (1) holding at least a tertiary-level degree, and (2) having completed secondary education or lower) and the influence of the parents on the students' decision to pursue a history teaching degree did not show a significant relationship (Pearson $\chi^2=0.053$).

We also investigated whether there is any correlation between the demographic location of the high school (type of settlement) and the influence of former history teachers on the students' decision to choose the history program. One student attended a capital city, 35 students attended a district seat city, 8 students attended a regional seat city, and 39 students attended a small town/village for their high school education.

Among these, 20 students (51%) reported that their former history teacher had an influence on their decision, and they completed their high school education in a small town or village. There were 23 students (66%) who indicated that their former history teacher had an influence on their decision and attended a district seat city for high school. Four students (50%) reported that their former history teacher had an influence on their decision and attended a regional seat city for high school. Only one student attended high school in a capital city. The demographic location of the high school and the influence of former history teachers on the students' decision to pursue a history program showed no significant relationship (Pearson $\chi^2=0.474$).

Students enrolled in the master's program (4th and 5th years) have already participated in pedagogical practice in recent years. We wanted to explore whether these students

encountered non-frontal teaching methods during their pedagogical practice. There are a total of 29 students in the two cohorts of the master's program. Two students did not respond to this question. Nine students reported that they had encountered non-frontal teaching methods, while 18 students stated that they had not encountered non-frontal teaching methods during their pedagogical practice.

The 5th-year students participated in teaching practice during the 2021/2022 academic year, during which they designed and implemented their own lessons. We wanted to find out whether these students had applied non-frontal teaching methods during their teaching practice. Out of the 19 5th-year students, 12 used non-frontal teaching methods, while 5 did not. Two students did not respond to this question.

We also examined whether, among the 12 graduates who applied non-frontal teaching methods during their teaching practice, 9 cases (75%) were influenced by their former history teacher to choose the history teaching profession, while in 3 cases (25%) their former history teacher did not have an influence on this decision.

Furthermore, we assessed whether the students would like to apply non-frontal teaching methods in the future as educators. Fifty-seven students expressed an interest in using non-frontal teaching methods, 3 students said they would not, 19 students did not respond to the question, and 4 students stated that they were unsure.

Of the 57 students who currently believe they would like to use non-frontal teaching methods in the future, 33 students (58%) reported that their former history teacher had the greatest influence on their decision to choose the history teaching profession. Among the 57 students, 10 were from the first year, 6 from the second year, 14 from the third year, 9 from the fourth year, and 18 from the fifth year. The data are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Year-Level Distribution of Students Influenced by Their History Teacher in Career Choice, and the Distribution of Bachelor's and Master's Students Who Intend to Use Alternative Teaching Methods in the Future (Beyond Frontal Teaching). n = 57

Source: own figure

The results of the undergraduate students are marked in blue. In the first row (blue columns), we can see the percentage of students in each cohort who were influenced by their history teacher in their career choice, while in the last row (orange and green columns), we can see the percentage of students in each cohort who think they would like to apply non-frontal teaching methods in the future. The columns for the fourth and fifth years are marked in green, as they represent the master's students. We examined whether there is a significant difference in the intention to use non-frontal teaching methods in the future depending on whether the students were influenced by their history teacher in their career choice. However, no significant difference was found (M-W U. Asymp. Sig. = 0.953).

Among the 54 undergraduate students, 32 students expressed a desire to use non-frontal teaching methods in the future as educators, while 22 did not. Of the 32 students, 20 were influenced by their former history teacher in their career choice, while 12 were not (Table 5). We examined whether there is a significant difference among the undergraduate students regarding the intention to use non-frontal teaching methods in the future depending on whether they were influenced by their history teacher in their career choice. However, no significant difference was found (M-W U. Asymp. Sig. = 0.563).

Table 5. Bachelor's Degree Students' Perceptions Regarding the Use of Work Formats in Relation to Former HT. n = 54

	As a teacher, I intend to apply instructional methods that differ from the traditional frontal teaching approach in the future.	As a teacher, I do not intend to apply instructional methods that differ from the traditional frontal teaching approach in the future.	Total
Students whose career choice was influenced by their history teacher;	20	12	32
Students whose career choice was not influenced by their history teacher.	12	10	22
Total	32	22	54

Source: Own table

Among the 29 master's students, 27 expressed a desire to use non-frontal teaching methods in the future as educators, while 2 did not. Of the 27 students, 14 were influenced by their former history teacher in their career choice, while 13 were not (Table 6). We examined whether there is a significant difference among the master's students regarding the intention to use non-frontal teaching methods in the future depending on whether they were influenced by their history teacher in their career choice. However, no significant difference was found (M-W U. Asymp. Sig. = 0.194).

We also examined whether there is a significant difference between the responses of undergraduate and graduate students regarding their intention to use non-frontal teaching methods in the future as educators. Of the 54 undergraduate students, 32 expressed a desire to use non-frontal teaching methods in the future, while of the 29

graduate students, 27 expressed the same intention (Table 7). Graduate students significantly more frequently expressed a desire to use non-frontal teaching methods in future history lessons (M-W U. Asymp Sig. = 0.001) compared to their undergraduate counterparts.

Table 6. Table 6: Master's Degree Students' Perceptions Regarding the Use of Work Formats in Relation to Former HT. n = 29

	As a teacher, I intend to apply instructional methods that differ from the traditional frontal teaching approach in the future.	As a teacher, I do not intend to apply instructional methods that differ from the traditional frontal teaching approach in the future.	Total
Students whose career choice was influenced by their history teacher;	14	2	16
Students whose career choice was not influenced by their history teacher.	13	0	13
Total	27	2	29

Source: Own table

Table 7: Students' Perceptions Regarding the Use of Work Formats Based on Their Academic Level. n = 83

	Bachelor's level students	Master's level students	Total
As a teacher, I intend to apply instructional methods that differ from the traditional frontal teaching approach in the future.	32	27	59
As a teacher, I do not intend to apply instructional methods that differ from the traditional frontal teaching approach in the future.	22	2	24
Total	54	29	83

Source: Own table

In this interpretation, however, it is important to mention that we did not examine the influence of the former history teachers on the students, but rather the impact of their university studies. This is because undergraduate students still rely more heavily on the experiences gained during their secondary education, whereas graduate students have already spent at least three full academic years in higher education, which affects their thinking, and they have also had teaching practice experience.

Answering the Research Questions

Regarding the first research question (Q1), which asks who had the greatest influence on the students' decision to choose the history teacher profession, the following can be concluded (Figure 1): of the 83 students who filled out the questionnaire:

- 1 student was influenced by a public figure
- 1 student was influenced by their private tutor

- 2 students were influenced by their former class teacher
- 5 students were influenced by another teacher (not a history teacher)
- 6 students were influenced by one of their parents
- 8 students were influenced by a relative
- 12 students were not influenced by anyone because they made the decision on their own
- 48 students were influenced by one of their former history teachers.

Among the 48 students who chose the teaching profession due to the influence of their history teacher, 23 were male and 25 were female. Among these 48 students, 23 graduated from a district-level city, 4 graduated from a district seat city, 1 graduated from a capital city, and 20 graduated from a small town.

Fourteen students stated that their family had the greatest influence on their career choice. Among these 14 students, 6 were influenced by one of their parents, and 8 were influenced by another relative. In 6 cases, there was a teacher in the student's family (in 1 case, the mother, in 2 cases, one of the grandparents, and in 3 cases, one of the siblings).

In total, 48 students (58% of the entire sample) reported that their history teacher had the greatest influence on their decision to choose the history teacher profession. This indicates that the influence of history teachers on career choices is significantly (One-Sided $p < 0,001$; Two-Sided $p < 0,001$) detectable.

Regarding the second research question (Q2), which asks about the teaching methods that students encountered during their secondary education history lessons, we can establish the following. Every student who completed the questionnaire encountered teacher explanation (the frontal teaching method) during their secondary education. In addition to teacher explanation, there were other teaching methods with which a significant portion of the respondents (at least 60%) encountered (worked with) at least a few times a month:

- **Teacher explanation with presentation** (HT: 75%; NHT: 60%)
- **Board outline** (HT: 77%; NHT: 62%)
- **Outlining and note-taking** (HT: 90%; NHT: 73%).

There were also teaching methods that approximately half of the students (40-59%) encountered (worked with) at least a few times a month:

- **Text processing** (HT: 54%; NHT: 52%)
- **Diagram and image analysis** (HT: 50%; NHT: 43%)
- **Map analysis** (HT: 55%; NHT: 49%)
- **Student presentations** (HT: 44%; NHT: 26%).

However, there were also teaching methods that only a smaller group of students (10-39%) encountered (worked with) at least a few times a month:

- **Data and dataset analysis** (HT: 35%; NHT: 32%)
- **Dramatic pedagogy methods (e.g., debates)** (HT: 33%; NHT: 14%)
- **Student inquiry and experimentation** (HT: 13%; NHT: 9%)

- **Teacher-led demonstration of investigation and experiments** (HT: 17%; NHT: 11%)
- **Film analysis/video analysis** (HT: 19%; NHT: 26%)
- **Drawing** (HT: 15%; NHT: 11%)
- **Project-based learning/project method** (HT: 23%; NHT: 17%).

We examined the students in this group to see if there were any common characteristics among them. We did not find any significant differences in terms of their gender (M-W U. Asymp. Sig. = 0.159), the type of settlement (K-W H. Asymp. Sig. = 0.534), or the influence of their history teachers (M-W U Asymp. Sig. = 0.280).

Among the listed methods, there were some that only a small group of students (0-9%) encountered (worked with) at least once a month:

- **Making models and dioramas** (HT: 0%; NHT: 0%)
- **Studying and analyzing pre-made models** (HT: 2%; NHT: 32%)
- **Media pedagogy methods (e.g., analyzing or creating advertisements)** (HT: 4%; NHT: 14%)
- **Using animation and simulation** (HT: 6%; NHT: 9%)
- **Field trips, museum visits, and practical exercises** (HT: 8%; NHT: 6%).

In most cases, we observed that students who were influenced by their history teacher in their career choice reported using more varied teaching methods. This suggests that a more diverse methodological repertoire might be associated with career choice in this sample.

We also grouped the students' responses based on whether they had encountered a particular method at least once during their high school studies or never encountered it. We then examined whether their history teacher had influenced their career choice. After analysing the data, we found that:

1. **Teacher explanation** was a method encountered by all students in their high school history classes;
2. **13 other methods** from the list of 19 were encountered more frequently by students who were influenced by their history teacher in their career decision.

From this, we can conclude that students who were influenced by their history teacher encountered a more diverse set of methods during their high school history lessons.

Regarding the choice of teaching methods, we referred to the study by Seres and Makádi (2022), in which 1,035 students were surveyed, and after excluding irrelevant responses, 1,011 students' answers were processed. The questionnaires were filled out online but under teacher supervision. The 1,011 students came from four different grades (8th, 9th, 10th, and 11th). Of these, 571 were elementary school students, and 437 were high school students. In their study, the authors concluded that the use of various sources was not very frequent. According to their findings, 85.14% of the elementary school students and 91.96% of the high school students encountered teacher explanation in every lesson. In our study, we asked university students about their high school (gymnasium) experiences, and the percentages are consistent with those found by Seres and Makádi (table 6, HT: 90%; NHT: 91%).

Seres and Makádi worked with a total of 22 teaching methods, of which we excluded two (use of globes and recognition tasks such as identifying minerals, rocks, and soils), as they are specific to geography and irrelevant to our study. The 22 methods (in our case, 20) were grouped into four categories:

1. **Teacher explanation**
2. **Source analysis**
3. **Active learning in class**
4. **Project-based learning.**

From the second group, Seres and Makádi's study found that the most common method among high school students was **diagram and image analysis** (35.31%). In our study, the most frequent method from the second category was **map analysis** (HT: 20%; NHT: 9%).

From the third group, Seres and Makádi found that the most common method used almost every lesson was **drawing** (43.91%). In our study, the most common method from the third group was **student presentations** (HT: 6%; NHT: 0%). It is important to note that in our study, the frequency of using methods from the third group in nearly every lesson was very low (below 6%).

The fourth group only included **project-based learning**. In Seres and Makádi's study, project-based learning was used in almost every lesson by 4.55% of high school students. In our study, this figure was higher (HT: 8%; NHT: 3%).

Conclusion

Before commencing the research, we posed the question whether the methodology of history teaching could change. The research revealed that educators play a significant role in students' career choices, as many students selected the teaching profession under the influence of their teachers. According to the responses of the history teacher students at Selye University, 58% of the entire sample (48 participants) reported that a former history teacher had influenced their decision to choose the history teacher program at university. We found that the influence of history teachers on students' career choices is statistically significant (One-Sided $p < 0.001$; Two-Sided $p < 0.001$).

During data analysis, it became evident that the diversity of the methodological repertoire also has a decisive effect on students' career choices. For those students who chose the teaching profession due to the influence of their former history teachers, it was apparent that they encountered a much more diverse range of teaching methods during their high school history classes compared to those who were not influenced by their history teachers in their decisions regarding further education (Tables 6 and 7).

The students' responses are highly promising regarding the methodological diversity for the future, as 69% of the students (57 participants) stated that they would like to apply non-frontal teaching methods and approaches in their future careers. Among these 57 students, 33 cases (58%) indicated that the former history teacher had the most significant impact on their decision to choose the history teacher program. Of these 57 students, 27 were male (61% of all male students) and 30 were female (77% of all female students). Among the 57 students, 10 were first-year, 6 second-year, 14 third-year, 9 fourth-year, and 18 fifth-year students (Figure 2). A total of 93% of the

master's students (27 participants) expressed the desire to use non-frontal teaching methods in the future, while this percentage was significantly lower for undergraduate students at 55% (30 participants). We determined that master's students have a significantly higher intention to apply non-frontal teaching methods compared to their undergraduate counterparts (M-W U Asymp.Sig.=0.001). This suggests that throughout their university studies, history teacher students' interest in using non-frontal teaching methods continuously increases, which can partly be attributed to the added value of university education. The influence of former history teachers on students' career choices across different years remains fairly consistent (50-64%). Based on these data, we can conclude that thanks to history teachers and university education, there is a strong likelihood that the methodological culture of history teaching will undergo a positive transformation in the near future.

The diverse application of various teaching methods is closely linked to the development of students' competencies, as competency development cannot be discussed without students' active participation in the educational process (Lappints 2002; Simándi 2016; Grave, Moust, Hommes 2003; Poort, Jansen, Hofman 2019; Schnider 2022).

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Appendix

Table 4. The Highest Level of Education Attained by the Students' Parents (n=83)

		Father's Highest Level of Education							
		Primary School	Secondary School without Final Examination (non-graduation)	Vocational Secondary School with Secondary School Leaving Certificate	Grammar School (Academic Secondary School)	Bachelor's Degree (Undergraduate Degree – BA/BSc)	Master's Degree (Graduate Degree – MA/MSc)	PhD	Total
Mother's Highest Level of Education	Primary School	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	5
	Secondary School without Final Examination (non-graduation)	2	15	6	1	0	0	0	24
	Vocational Secondary School with Secondary School Leaving Certificate	0	4	20	0	1	3	2	30
	Grammar School (Academic Secondary School)	0	2	1	1	0	1	0	5
	Bachelor's Degree (Undergraduate Degree – BA/BSc)	0	2	6	1	1	0	0	10
	Master's Degree (Graduate Degree – MA/MSc)	0	1	5	0	0	3	0	9
	Total	3	28	38	3	2	7	2	83

Source: Own table

